

»Going Dark«. Data tracking and data access at European level¹

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It sounds as if Brussels wants to become a cyberpunk metropolis: an expert group that is not allowed to be called that so that you can't know who its members are. Data access to devices, services and infrastructures whenever the »security« deems it necessary. Influence on industry standards so that this is always possible in real time. If not, it is regrettable that vulnerabilities will have to be exploited and penalties imposed on those who do not »co-operate«. What even the name - *Going Dark* - makes it look like the scorched no-man's land between *Neuromancer* and *V for Vendetta*, has an administrative designation: »High-Level Group on Access to Data for Effective Law Enforcement«. The far-reaching proposals of this EU working group were rated as „impressive and forward-looking“ by the Hungarian government and are to become the focus of the current Council Presidency. And always at the centre of this development, in past and present: scientific infrastructures.

Democracy has its paradoxes. For example, Christian Stöcker recently pointed out in the ZEVEDI podcast *Digitalgespräch* (Stöcker 2024) that lying cannot be banned in a democracy, because in order to enforce such a ban, a central »truth authority« would be needed, and then we would no longer have a democracy, but a totalitarian regime. A form of society that draws its development fundamentally from a reason-led discourse of shared better insight can therefore only defend itself against the manipulation of its foundations to a limited extent, but is dependent on workarounds, which sometimes work better and - in times of troll armies and news deserts - sometimes worse. A liberal democracy is therefore fragile in its structures with a certain necessity, and we have already experienced in our German history that it can even be abolished in a more or less democratic way. That was an extreme, but there are also (so far) less far-reaching and more insidious processes in which fundamental rights are fought with the help of fundamental rights. Processes of this kind have characterised our digital world for decades.

Digital law enforcement

Much of what makes up the current conflict in Brussels has its origins in the 1980s with a cocaine smuggler who switched sides.² When Hank Asher - a little-known data pioneer in Europe - found his business too hot to handle, he offered himself to the Drug Enforcement Administration (DEA) as an informant. He found his calling there, as the DEA was one of the very early *law enforcement agencies* to work with a centralised database: suspects were recorded in the system, given an identifier and stored there forever. Asher learnt quickly, acquired hardware and set up his own company in 1992. His initial customers were the

¹ This text is a machine-based translation of the weblog article »Going Dark. Datentracking und Datenzugriff auf europäischer Ebene« in order to provide easier access for non-German speaking interested parties, also the German language quotes were therefore transferred. Consider this version a »post-print derivative« and please refer to the original in case of references or citations: Siems, Renke (2024): „Going Dark“. Datentracking und Datenzugriff auf europäischer Ebene. In: Verantwortungsblog. <https://zevedi.de/going-dark-datentracking-und-datenzugriff-auf-europaischer-ebene/>. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.60805/p7w9-d268>

² The presentation here follows Funk 2023 and my review of the book in the library journal *o-bib* (Siems 2024a), from which some sentences were also taken for this article.

insurance industry, to whom he wanted to sell what is now part of digital *risk solutions*: data that can be used to calculate loss events in advance and, ideally, automate processes. When collecting driving licence and number plate data, he understood something that could be called the fundamental rights loop, which all data brokers have exploited since him: Data protection and freedom of information laws had been around for decades, but the rights they established, such as informational self-determination, were conceived in the same way as freedom of science, for example - as a right of defence against the state. The state should not be able to keep secrets from its citizens, but citizens should be able to keep secrets from the state. Apparently, Hank Asher wasn't the state, so he found himself a lawyer and began to extract the data from the public authorities: Vehicle owners, registry office data, severe disabilities, properties, licences, address changes, insolvencies flooded into his servers, were processed into personal profiles and offered to his clients. In 1997, the dam broke and he also received data from credit card and utility companies. This made Asher's *AutoTrack* product inescapable, because all the mechanisms that we use today against the tracking of digital advertising, for example, did not apply in this universe of hard real-time data: there is no such thing as an opt-out for the registry office that notarises my marriage and no right to be forgotten for the energy supplier that is supplying my computer with electricity at this very moment.

This inevitability led Asher back to law enforcement, now as an interested customer - starting with Leigh McMorrow, an IT employee from a neighbouring police department, to whom he demonstrated his product.

„'How are you doing that?' she wondered aloud. He explained that he was gathering public records to build a product for the insurance industry. 'I was just so flabbergasted,' McMorrow says. 'The minute he showed it to me, I'm like, my God, oh my God. I said 'You're sitting on a gold mine. Law enforcement will eat this up with a spoon.'“ (Funk 2023, 73)

And so it came to pass and the loop of fundamental rights tightened: the state, which was not allowed to have any secrets, rented access to those of its citizens via non-governmental third parties. In the world after 9/11, *data fusion solutions* developed into a multi-billion market with annual growth rates of 15 to 20 per cent (Verified Market Research 2024, Chemical Industry Latest 2023), surpassed only by the explosive amounts of data generated by social media and advertising tracking. The areas of application have also grown, with facial recognition, for example, creating a new inescapability as a digital tool for monitoring the offline world: „You could delete your social media account. You could leave your phone at home. You couldn't leave your face at home.“ (Funk 2023, 197) Data fusion not only leads to profiling, but also to more and more scoring in both the public and commercial sectors. What *social credit scores* are in China, an ever-increasing number of scores are in the western world: *renter scores, juror scores, voter scores, customer-lifetime-value scores, welfare-benefits scores* - and in the pandemic, *socioeconomic health scores* that justify measures and the distribution of resources.

Although the market for data fusion is large, the relevant market participants are rather small in number and some of the market leaders are also very well known in the scientific community: RELX (the parent company of Elsevier), Thomson Reuters, Clarivate and Palantir. The reason why some of the well-known science suppliers are at the forefront here is due to the digitalisation of science: Elsevier, for example, still had an overwhelming paper quota for its

published journals in the years around 2000. Fearing that it would be overrun by the up-and-coming Internet, the publisher looked for an alternative, and when Hank Asher's health increasingly burnt out and his company was up for sale, Elsevier seized the opportunity and merged Asher's legacy with its own data service LexisNexis. Early Investments were also made in Palantir in 2006. (RELX 2021)

Since then, leading providers of scientific services have been growing into the *risk solutions sector*, supplying data products for *predictive policing* (Wang et al. 2022) and increasingly re-importing the working methods of this sector back to science. Years ago, the DFG already reported on data tracking in science and how the former publishers are now equipping their platforms with monitoring technologies as data analytics companies (DFG 2021) - only to discover that the negotiations on the major DEAL open access contracts have only partially resulted in a legally compliant situation. (Altschaffel et al. 2024) Having long been accustomed to scoring with questionable indicators, science governance is now being offered international »research intelligence« along the lines of *law enforcement* and is taking advantage of it - without apparently giving much thought to what the acquisition of these »insights« means for researchers in terms of risks, what knowledge and technology outflow is possible as a result and what new opportunities are also available for the *merchants of doubt*, using these structures and incentive systems to lead science into the same quagmire in which a large part of the news industry already lies and which can also lead to the replacement of the previously common factual basis with the competition of competing narratives (Siems 2024b) and bring scientific infrastructures ever closer to the *fantasy industrial complex* that Renée DiResta describes. (DiResta 2024)

And now the EU?

The EU initiative »Going Dark« has grown out of this ground and appears to have set out to escalate developments once again. Driven by the fear that law enforcement could go dark due to the spread and progress of encryption technologies, the aforementioned High Level Group was set up under the Swedish Council Presidency in June 2023. (European Commission 2023) The group was originally supposed to bring in a variety of perspectives, not just law enforcement and criminal justice, but also data protection and privacy, cybersecurity, the private sector, non-governmental organisations and academia. This does not seem to have happened - the High Level Group itself sank into darkness, so to speak (FragDenStaat 2023) - Member lists were blacked out and, apart from the European Data Protection Supervisor as a guest, law enforcement and its environment seem to be among themselves. The main steps of the expert group will now take place during the Hungarian Council Presidency: the publication of the recommendations (European Commission 2024) took place in the immediate run-up, the final report will be published in the autumn when the work programme of the new Commission will also be published. Finally, the Council of the European Union will meet in December to discuss the topic (Council of the European Union 2024). Hungary has explicitly included „retention and access to law enforcement data“ in its work programme. (Hungarian Presidency 2024)

The »Going Dark« group is focussing its work on three areas: Access to data on end devices, access to data held by providers and access to data flows. A particular focus is on over-the-top

(OTT) services, which compete with traditional telecommunication services such as messaging and video telephony. International cooperation outside the EU is also emphasised, with the USA being mentioned here. The group also attaches great importance to linking its ideas with existing regulations, with the Digital Services Act being mentioned several times as a starting point.

With regard to device data, the group complains about the lack of cooperation between manufacturers and law enforcement, which is why it is very difficult to legally extract data from the device and make it usable in court without encryption and with the necessary metadata. Two things are therefore key: on the one hand, law enforcement must exert more influence on the standardisation committees than it has to date and thus shape protocols, interfaces and technical architectures so that future technical standards are developed accordingly from the outset. Secondly, if the industry does not cooperate voluntarily, obligations should be imposed on it.

When it comes to provider data, the topic of data retention inevitably comes up, which is dealt with emphatically and in detail far beyond traditional telecommunications services: OTT services in particular are supposed to „create transparency“ about the data they generate, process and store. Interestingly, car manufacturers are also seen as communication services and instruments are discussed to enforce compliance among those who are currently raving about the »connectivity« of their new models and making access to the European market dependent on it. „The opportunity to legislate on data already in the possession of providers for business purposes“ was also discussed. This could mean many things: Access to user data across the board, as the Data Act understands it, or access to data brokers' databases, as their most popular product, personalized localisation data, is also mentioned in this context.

Data flows require the Group to deal with large volumes of data in real time. Standardisation should therefore also be influenced here, for example with 5G/6G. In the case of uncooperative providers, it will probably still be necessary to resort to the use of vulnerabilities; here and overall, encryption would therefore be very much in the way: „law enforcement authorities need to have a pre-established lawful access to readable data“ - which is why initiatives such as Apple's Private Relay are not at all welcome.

In detail, the recommendations then propose, among other things, more money for research and development to obtain data (No. 4), improving the use of vulnerabilities (No. 6), involving the scientific community (No. 8), expanding the ability to transfer large data sets in real time (No. 9) and - in addition to No. 6 - apparently the targeted cracking of devices and services if the data cannot be accessed in any other way (No. 10). The influence on technical standards should cover the entire spectrum of the Internet of Things, such as *connected cars* and satellite communication (No. 20). Manufacturers of hardware and software, as well as cybersecurity, data protection and standardisation experts, should be more closely involved in a „technology roadmap“, „in order to implement lawful access by design in all relevant technologies in line with the needs expressed by law enforcement“ (No. 22). The aim is an „EU-level handbook“ of relevant legislation (No. 25), „a harmonised EU regime on data retention“ (No. 27) and also a harmonisation of criminal law tools to enforce cooperation, including imprisonment (No. 34).

Overall, centralisation efforts away from the member states towards EU institutions can be observed, which are to serve as a »single point of contact« for companies, for example.

In view of the fact that there were clearly no snowflakes at work here and the plans go far beyond what has previously caused a furore under the label of chat control, the public response to this sprawling surveillance package has so far been surprisingly muted. Working in the administrative underground, a topic that is usually rather unattractive for traditional press coverage due to its technical complexity, and an apparently silent and far-reaching consensus among many member states have contributed to the fact that no broad discourse has emerged so far, even though everyone in a European country will be affected. It looks as if the European public has grown tired of the longstanding debate on surveillance.

What happens?

So far, the topic has mainly been addressed by selected tech press outlets such as *Netzpolitik* and members of the European Parliament. Patrick Breyer deserves special mention here, who has persistently pursued this issue³ - only for the EU Commission to ignore a question from him for months until he resigned from the EU Parliament after the elections. (European Parliament 2024) If we summarise the digital activist criticism in a deliberately exaggerated way, we are faced with the accusation of a »Stasi 4.0«: a security apparatus that has been completely let off the hook and no longer has any interest in being contained by fundamental rights and civil liberties. Whether one shares the severity of the criticism or not, one will have to admit when looking at the catalogue of measures that it is highly invasive - law enforcement wants to be in the driver's seat, and alone. And if the recommendation paper repeatedly refers to the fact that all of this will not weaken end-to-end encryption and that data protection and privacy are secured, this will have to be interpreted like the »technological openness« in climate policy: a decorative wording that contributes nothing to the issue but is intended to distract.

It should also be noted that »going dark« in itself has little to do with reality, but is above all a carefully cultivated political myth. Time and again, high-ranking studies such as the Berkman Center for Internet and Society at Harvard University have shown that the fears are unfounded. (Berkman Center 2016) Law enforcement agencies now have much more information at their disposal than in the past and are achieving corresponding investigative success. In some cases, »creative« solutions are used, as in the story told by Joseph Cox of the secure communication platform Anom, which spread in organised crime with the small catch that it was operated covertly by the FBI. Internationally, authorities were able to observe their customers as if they were in a goldfish bowl and strike. (Cox 2024) But even there the limits were already apparent, as this honey pot was so successful that it began to get out of hand, and the usability of the evidence in court is also often called into question.

Ultimately, the catalogue of measures also revisits all the debates that took place during the negotiations on the Data Act, for example, with regard to the protection of trade secrets. »Access by design« would mean access on demand to services, consumer goods, industrial production, research and development. Are we sure that car manufacturers in Europe, for example, will enthusiastically support this? If this nevertheless prevails, it would also discredit

³ See the topic page he created under Breyer 2024.

the European data strategy that has been so painstakingly developed, as the Digital Services Act mentioned in the measures as a starting point has already been followed like a shadow by accusations of encouraging authoritarian developments behind the facade of the rule of law. (e.g. European Digital Rights 2022)

However, the outlook for citizens in Europe is more decisive and, unlike that of the security authorities, is very bleak indeed. „A VPN won't help either,“ explains Jan Jonsson from Mullvad. „It would mean total surveillance and that Europe's inhabitants carry state spyware in their pockets.“ (Jonsson 2024) What is still little discussed here is that, in an emergency, the sheer scale of the invasive interventions will lead to huge amounts of data and a corresponding need for processing, creating new demand for trusted service providers in law enforcement: Palantir is already woven into the German security infrastructure, although ongoing court cases show that the creation of facts there relates more to data access than valid legal bases. (Abbe 2023) LexisNexis already has access to the European data strategy by entering the field of mobility data. (LexisNexis Risk Solutions 2020) While the large platforms such as Google, Amazon and Microsoft have increasingly *developed* into *military contractors* in recent years,⁴ the specialised platforms - the »GAFAM of curated information« originating from the scientific sector - have continued to conquer the internal security market with their *data fusion solutions*. The professional record of these companies is extremely mixed: Sarah Lamdan had already analysed for the scientific sector that what she calls »data cartels« are by no means achieving better performance with the strong growth in data volumes and the introduction of AI applications (Lamdan 2022), while McKenzie Funk refers to reports by the US Senate that found countless data protection violations, „but - despite an estimated billion dollars in taxpayer support - no evidence they had helped stop any terror attacks.“ (Funk 2023, 184) Instead, deportation centres are preferably filled with easy-to-find people through *data-driven deportation*: Mothers who are arrested in front of their young children, employees at work - and likewise prisons with those who fall victim to false evidence. Funk tells the story of John Newsome, for example, who was robbed of his hard-won livelihood by the sloppy operation of LexisNexis. He managed not to sign a guilty plea and get a lawyer, so he sees himself as favoured because „there's plenty of people that could tell you the story that I'm telling you right now. But they're gonna tell it to you, and the ending of theirs is gonna be like, 'and when I got out of jail fifteen years later...‘“ (Funk 2023, 189)

What is now known as »AdInt«, the merging of advertising tracking and *risk solutions* into »advertising intelligence«, is particularly error-prone (Meineck/Dachwitz 2024) and at the same time the most prominent form of an uncanny alliance between the tech industry and politics on the way to ever more surveillance. (Tau 2024) The data broker industry, which is linked to *risk solutions*, is now itself considered a „hidden security crisis“ (Cracked Labs 2023): Employees in critical infrastructures, military personnel, employees of intelligence services can be identified in the rampantly traded data, their movement patterns and everyday actions can be traced. (Brunner et al. 2024, Meineck/Dachwitz 2024) This also applies to science, as the *Xandr-leak* last year also revealed evidence that LexisNexis, for example, passed on data from protected professional groups such as lawyers and researchers to the data broker LiveRamp.⁵

⁴ See e.g. Microsoft 2024 and Biddle 2024.

⁵ See Keegan/Eastwood 2023 and the GitHub repository linked there.

The trackers, fingerprinters and audience tools anchored on the science platforms also collect data on an ongoing basis. (Siems 2022) This not only poses a risk to individuals, but as this data is very widely available and low-threshold, it also poses a risk of research and technology leakage. While the G7 jostle for position with China over scientific espionage and risk diplomatic anger (Gabel 2024; Directorate-General for Research and Innovation 2024), the virtual barn gates to sensitive data from highly cultivated research teams are wide open all the time.

A conclusion - not only in terms of science policy

If risk solutions themselves harbour such great risks, what is the motivation behind "Going Dark"? Why this unconditional will to enforce anti-democratic measures? Does the much-vaunted systemic competition between China and the Western world ultimately not exist because everyone actually wants to become Chinese and combine capital and control as happily as possible? Perhaps we need to go back to the beginning of the story, where Hank Asher first demonstrated *AutoTrack* to policewoman McMorrow. She organised a demo in her police department and exactly what she had in mind happened: „The chief, the deputy chief, all the detectives [...] freaked out over it, absolutely freaked out over it.“ (Funk 2023, 73) Data fusion has a strong seductive power due to its glamour of (apparent) evidence and because the security authority can skip all constitutional (and therefore strenuous) checks and balances: you no longer need a court order, you no longer have to be questioned, you can get everything you want on the fly via *data shopping* - an *all you can eat* for personal data. As a public authority, you don't even have to question yourself and the perhaps no longer quite up-to-date forms of work and the official undergrowth, because *data fusion* still puts everything right and shiny at your feet. The fact that it is full of errors can be ignored; after all, it is not the users who are affected, but those who are recorded, such as the librarian Shea Swauger, who, in a self-experiment, retrieved his profile from the LexisNexis competitor Thomson Reuters: 41 pages of the most detailed information - but many of them incorrect, right down to the gender.⁶

When we talk about responsibility in the context of »Going Dark«, we are not only talking about the freedom of scientists, but also about the fundamental rights of citizens and the basic functions and processes of our society. This could be the economy, it could be our coexistence as such - but are we also talking enough about what all this should mean for academic freedom if, in future, all devices in laboratories and offices are to have a dedicated line to *law enforcement*? All services that are (also) used by researchers will have a duty to cooperate in prosecution? How should research data infrastructures, on which a large part of future value creation depends, but also of digital social development as a whole, develop further? How can data altruism be motivated if everyone can honestly just reply: »Thank you - I've already donated!«

It is therefore questionable in various respects where a lot of things are both in the dark and in disarray.

⁶ „To wrap it up, @Westlaw, through CLEAR, collects a shit ton of data about you. They share it with law enforcement, including @ICEgov, and anyone who has enough money to buy CLEAR. And for most people, there's nothing you can do about it.“ (Swauger 2019)

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